

Local Government in Canada

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Contents

1. The System of Local Government in Canada: An Introduction.....	1
2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Canada: An Introduction	11
2.2. <i>Governing the Construction of Transit Infrastructure in Toronto and Vancouver</i>	15
3.1. Local Financial Arrangements in Canada: An Introduction.....	20
3.2. <i>Property Tax Reliance and the Re-Emergence of Provincial Funding Transfers to Local Government in Ontario</i>	22
4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Canada: An Introduction	27
4.2. <i>Beyond Municipal Amalgamations in Ontario</i>	29
5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Canada: An Introduction.....	34
5.2. <i>Representing Toronto’s Distinct Interests to the Ontario Provincial Government</i>	36
6.1. People’s Participation in Local Decision-Making in Canada: An Introduction	40
6.2. <i>Adopting Ranked-Choice Voting in London, Ontario</i>	43

Structure of Local Government

4.1. The Structure of Local Government in Canada: An Introduction

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As noted in report section 1, the structure of local government varies greatly by province across Canada, more so even than the structure of local financial arrangements. As a result, we will only focus on Ontario in this introductory section. The basic outlines of Ontario's local government structures were established by the Baldwin Act of 1849. It laid out a rural governance model that consisted of upper-tier counties, each of which included a number of lower-tier municipalities (townships, villages, etc.) that managed strictly local affairs. In addition, it established provisions for the creation of single-tier 'separated cities' once a settlement reached 10,000 in population. The growth of urban areas under this system of local government was dealt with by provincially authorized annexations through which separated cities gradually absorbed surrounding countryside. This basic structure of local government remained largely unchanged until the 1950s. Indeed, even today, over half of Ontario's population lives either in two-tier rural municipalities, or in one of 31 single-tier cities.

Starting in the 1950s, however, the Ontario provincial government began to respond to rapid and large-scale urban growth (primarily in the Toronto area) in a different way, by establishing two-tier systems of local government designed to finance and coordinate urban development. The primary rationale for these innovations was enhancing capacity for planning, infrastructure development and service delivery. The first such system was the Metropolitan Toronto – a federation of 13 formerly autonomous municipalities established in 1954. This was followed in the early 1970s by a wave of provincially-created 'regional municipalities' that covered most of the large urbanizing areas in the province, including those that surrounded Metropolitan Toronto.

A further major wave of structural change came in the late 1990s. At this time, a conservative provincial government – emphasizing efficiency and cost reduction rather than increased local government capacity – embarked on a massive program of municipal amalgamations. Amalgamations occurred in both rural and urban areas, with many formerly two-tier rural systems being amalgamated into single-tier municipalities. The provincial government imposed these structural reforms in a top-down manner, with relatively little local consultation. As a result, between 1995 and 2002, the number of municipalities in Ontario decreased from 850 to 444 (which is also the current number).⁵⁵

Many of the amalgamations of the late 1990s faced local political opposition, which was largely unsuccessful, since the province has full control over local government structure. Doubtless

⁵⁵ André Côté and Michael Fenn, *Provincial-Municipal Relations in Ontario: Approaching an Inflection Point* (Institute on Municipal Finance and Governance 2014) 11.

the most controversial amalgamation was that of Metropolitan Toronto, the two-tier system from 1954, which was merged into a single, large City of Toronto. No significant structural reform to local government has taken place in Ontario over the last 20 years.⁵⁶

References to Scientific and Non-Scientific Publications

Côté A and Fenn M, *Provincial-Municipal Relations in Ontario: Approaching an Inflection Point* (Institute on Municipal Finance and Governance 2014)

Spicer Z, *The Boundary Bargain: Growth, Development, and the Future of City County Separation* (McGill-Queen's Press 2016)

⁵⁶ The reasons for this are discussed in report section 4.1. Beyond Municipal Amalgamations in Ontario.

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